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OVERVIEW OF PUBLIC PROCUREMENT ACT, 2007 (AS AMENDED)

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Abstract

The Public Procurement Act, 2007 was enacted following an assessment by the World Bank in 1999 which exposed Nigeria as having ineffective procurement process bedeviled with corruption. The Act was an attempt by Nigeria to provide a legal and regulatory framework to curb the excesses in government activities and businesses with a view to ensuring proper regulation in the procurement process. This paper adopts a doctrinal methodology by reviewing literature in the related field. The paper gives an overview of the Public Procurement Act, 2007 as amended and also the challenges in the implementation of the Act. The paper finds that although Nigeria has taken a milestone in enacting a law regulating public procurement process, there are quite a number of bottlenecks towards its implementation. The most prominent ones are corruption and political interference in the procurement process. The paper finally recommends the government to tighten its belt in the war against corruption, reduce political interference and also to implement sanctions on erring public officials and persons that violates the provisions of the Act.

Keywords: Competition, Corruption, Public Procurement

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Public procurement reform in Nigeria, like in many other African countries is attributable to the World Bank.¹ In 1999, the World Bank conducted assessment of the state of the Nigeria's public procurement system and discovered that procurement processes were fraught with a lot of irregularities,² bordering on gross corruption.³ Prior to the publication of the World Bank's Country Assessment Report on the Nigerian Procurement system in 2000,⁴ Nigeria did not have any clear cut policy on procurement. What Nigeria had back then were series of financial guidelines issued by the minister of finance regulating public procurement.⁵ Those guidelines were of course subject to review at the instance of the minister at any time the minister deems it fit.⁶ Therefore, issuing these regulations were at the pleasure of the minister of finance, it was difficult to have any transparency, consistency, predictability or accountability in the process, and above all, there was no any mechanism in place to ensure strict compliance with the guidelines issued by the minister.⁷

There is indeed no underestimating the importance of a robust public procurement system as it is one of the drivers of economic development. However, when it is fraught with irregularities as was the case in Nigeria before the World Bank Assessment report, it was bound to throw a spanner in the country's development. In order to help arrest the debilitating situation of the lack of progress of the Nigeria's economy the World Bank

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¹ Sope Williams-Elegbe, 'A Comparative Analysis of the Nigerian Public Procurement Act Against International Best Practice' [2015] (59) *Journal of African Law*, 1, P 85-98; see also World Bank, Nigeria, Country Procurement Assessment Report, Volume II: Main Text and Annexes 5, [2000]; see also World Bank, Nigeria, Country Procurement Assessment Report, Volume I: Summary of Findings and Recommendations 5, [2000].

² Ibid, these irregularities consist of the fact that Nigeria did not have a public procurement law, neither did it have any institution saddled with the responsibility of issuing guidelines and or ensuring those guidelines are adhered to by the procuring agencies.

³ World Bank, Nigeria, Country Procurement Assessment Report, note 1.

⁴ Sope Williams-Elegbe, 'A Comparative Analysis of the Nigerian Public Procurement Act' note 1

⁵ See World Bank, Nigeria, Country Procurement Assessment Report, note 1.

⁶ Sope Williams-Elegbe, 'A Comparative Analysis of the Nigerian Public Procurement Act' note 1

⁷ See Sope Williams-Elegbe, 'The Reform and Regulation of Public Procurement in Nigeria' [2012] (41) *Public Contract Law Journal*, 2, pp 339-366

conducted the Country Assessment of the public procurement practice. This paper conducted a general overview of the public Procurement Act (2007) as amended.

2.0 WHAT IS PUBLIC PROCUREMENT?

The Act in section 60 defines public procurement as “the acquisition by any means of obtaining goods; works or services by the government.”⁸ Public procurement can also be defined as “the acquisition, whether under formal contract or not, of works, supplies and services by public bodies”. It ranges from the purchase of routine supplies of or services to formal tendering and placing contracts for large infrastructural projects.⁹ Public procurement can also be defined as the act of buying, leasing or otherwise obtaining commodities or services. It includes the process of acquiring commodities and services such as description of requirements, selection and solicitation, preparation which ends with the award of contract for the acquisition or disposal of commodities as the case may be.¹⁰

In the same vein, public procurement can as well be defined as “...the process by which organizations acquire goods and services using public funds. It involves planning, inviting offers, awarding contracts and managing contracts.”¹¹ From the foregoing we can understand what public procurement means or involves.

Almost all government’s expenditure and disposal of its own property are expected to be done through an acceptable procurement process. Lack of a well-founded legal regime in that respect would certainly pave way to a lot of irregularities. The World Bank in its report observed that Nigeria was very much ripe for reform in the public procurement. Consequently, based on the recommendations in the report, Nigeria enacted the Public

⁸ Section 60

⁹ Onyedikachi Okere and Ngozi Maureen Idih, ‘A Legal Overview of the Public Procurement Act 2007 (as Amended 2016)’ [2018] (Vol. 5, Issue 3) *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, p 22.

¹⁰ Robert E. Lloyd and Clifford P. McCue, ‘What is Public Procurement? Definitional Problems and Implications’ [2004] (3) *International Public Procurement Conference Proceedings*, p 6

¹¹ Mohammed Yahaya, ‘Public Procurement Act, 2007 and Contracting Business in Nigeria: Case Study of Public Sector Organizations’ [2020] *International Journal of Scientific Research*. Available at www.researchgate.net, last visited 13/08/2021.

Procurement Act, 2007.¹² The Act was modeled after the UNCITRAL Model Law on Procurement of Goods, Construction and Services.¹³

3.0 THE PUBLIC PROCUREMENT ACT, 2007 (AS AMENDED)

The Public Procurement Act, 2007 as amended, was passed into law by the Nigerian National Assembly in 2007, with the objective of providing the necessary legal regime for public procurement which would ensure all federal public procurement institutions conduct their procurement in the most transparent, just, timely and free from any undue influence from both civil servants and politicians. The Act is made up of thirteen parts across 61 sections and covers issues ranging from establishment of the Bureau of Public Procurement and a Governing Council that is saddled with the responsibility of overseeing the activities of the Bureau, in carrying out the processes of procurement, qualification of contractors, procurement contracts thresholds, pecuniary measures in the event of contravening the provisions of the Act by both procurement entities and contractors and other ancillary provisions.

The next sections will examine the provisions of the Act.

4.0 ESTABLISHMENT OF NATIONAL COUNCIL ON PUBLIC PROCUREMENT AND BUREAU OF PUBLIC PROCUREMENT

Parts I and II of the Act establishes the two institutions responsible for monitoring, regulating and standard settings of public procurement. The National Council on Public Procurement and Bureau of Public Procurement were established. Section 1 and 2 established the Council and provide for its membership and functions. The Council shall have the Minister of Finance as its Chairman, including the Attorney General of the Federation and such other members who are to be appointed by the President to hold office for the period they remain in office as political holders.¹⁴

¹² No 65 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria.

¹³ United Nations Commission on International Trade Law: Model on Procurement of Goods, Construction and Services, 1994, 34 I.L.M. 718. In 1994, the UNCITRAL enacted the model law for countries enacting procurement laws for the first time or those reforming their existing procurement laws to adopt same for that purpose. See also Carolined Nicholas, Reform of the UNCITRAL Model Law on Procurement, Eur. Bank for Reconstruction and Development, 2010.

¹⁴ See section 1 (5) of the Act.

Section 2 of the Act provides for the functions of the Council which are: to consider, approve and amend the monetary thresholds¹⁵ for the procuring entities.¹⁶ It is also the responsibility of the Council to “approve policies on public procurement” and receive and consider for approval the appointment of the Directors of the Bureau.¹⁷

Section 3 of the Act established the Bureau of Public Procurement, a body corporate with perpetual succession, capable of acquiring, holding and disposing of its own property which can also sue and be sued as the case maybe.¹⁸

Sections 4, 5 and 6 provide for the objectives, functions and powers of the Bureau. Whereas Section 4 of the Act provides for the objectives of the Bureau as being responsible for harmonizing government policies on public procurement and to ensure accountability, probity and transparency in the procurement process.¹⁹ It is also to ensure the entrenchment of fair, competitive and transparent practices in the procurement and disposal of public assets.²⁰

In trying to entrench these principles in the public procurement system, the Bureau under section 5 is to exercise a wide range of functions such as to “formulate the general policies and guidelines relating to public sector procurement for the approval of the Council.”²¹ Other functions of the Bureau is supervising the implementation of procurement policies, publishing contract details in procurement journals, undertaking research and surveys in procurement, organize training and programmes for procurement professionals, review procurement and the award of contract procedures periodically, and to also establish an internet portal to serve as a primary source of information on all procurements in government entities, amongst others.²²

¹⁵ Monetary threshold “means the value limit in Naira set by the Bureau outside of which an approving authority may not award a procurement contract”. See section 60 of the Act.

¹⁶ Section 2

¹⁷ See section 2 (a-f)

¹⁸ Section 3 (1) (a-c)

¹⁹ Section 4 (a)

²⁰ Ibid (b-d); see also the International Organization for Standardization distilled the primary objectives of public procurement to be fairness, equity, transparency, competition and cost effectiveness; ISO 10845; see also Sope Williams-Elegbe, ‘A Comparative Analysis of the Nigerian Public Procurement Act Against International Best Practice’ note 1, p 86. The Public Procurement Act, 2007 as amended appears to make provisions for the entrenchment of these objectives.

²¹ Section 5 (a)

²² See generally section 5 (b-s)

5.0 POWERS OF THE BUREAU

Section 6 of the Act lists a number of things that the Bureau has powers to effect. The Bureau should have powers to enforce the monetary threshold to be set by the Council for the procurement entities to apply.²³ The Bureau should also have powers to “issue certificate of ‘No Objection’²⁴ for contract award within the prior review threshold for all procurements within the purview of this Act”.²⁵ The Bureau should have powers to inspect and review procurement contracts for the purposes of ensuring compliance,²⁶ debar contractors, suppliers, or service providers who are found contravening the provision of the Act,²⁷ to maintain national database of contractors and service providers;²⁸ to recommend to the Council in cases of persistent breaches of the Act for necessary disciplinary measures to be imposed on the erring entities or individuals as the case maybe.²⁹

The bureau is also to act as the Secretariat for the Council,³⁰ and can subject to the approval of the Council enter into contracts, partnership with firms or individuals as the case maybe to enable it discharge its functions as specified in the Act.³¹

6.0 STAFF OF THE BUREAU

Sections 7, 8 and 9 of the Act makes provisions for the staff of the Bureau which consist of the Director General as the chief executive and accounting officer of the Bureau to be appointed by the President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria on the recommendation of the Council.³²

Section 8, 9 and 10 provide for the appointment of principal and other officers of the Bureau with their qualifications, entitlements and conditions of service respectively.³³

²³ Section 6 (1) (a)

²⁴ Certificate of no objection is defined by section 60 as “the document evidencing and authenticating that due process and the letters of this Act have been followed in the conduct of a procurement proceeding and allowing for the procuring entity to enter into a contract or effect payments to contractors or suppliers from the treasury.” See also section 6 (1) (b).

²⁵ Section 6 (1) (b)

²⁶ Ibid (6) (1) (d) (i)

²⁷ Ibid (6) (1) (e)

²⁸ Ibid (6) (1) (f)

²⁹ Ibid (6) (1) (i) (i-v)

³⁰ Ibid (6) (2)

³¹ Ibid (6) (3)

³² See section 7 of the Act.

³³ See generally sections 8, 9 and 10 of the Act.

7.0 FUNDS FOR THE BUREAU

Section 12 makes provision for the establishment, subject to the approval of the Council, for the funds of the Bureau where monies appropriated to the Bureau by the National Assembly are to be credited;³⁴ “all subventions, fees and charges for services rendered...”³⁵ to be equally credited and all other assets accruable to the Bureau are to be deposited.³⁶

The Bureau can equally charge from this Fund to settle all its expenditure, offset administrative costs, pay salaries and remuneration of the staff of the Bureau, its experts and professionals, etc.³⁷

Section 13 provides for the financial year of the Bureau for the purpose of budgeting and annual reporting, which is to be the same with that of the Federal Government.³⁸

The creation of the Bureau has provided a central entity that the Federal Government’s contractors and the general public can approach for any complaints in respect of public procurement at the Federal Government level. This was not the case prior to the creation of the Bureau as the mode of receiving and addressing complaints was fragmented.³⁹

8.0 APPLICATION OF THE PUBLIC PROCUREMENT ACT

Part III of the Act provides for the scope of application of the Act. The Act applies to all procurement of goods, works and services by the Federal Government and entities under it, subject to the Provisions of the Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission (Establishment) Act, 2005.⁴⁰ The Act defines procurement entity to mean “any public body engaged in procurement and includes a ministry, extra ministerial office, government agency, parastatal, and corporation.”⁴¹

³⁴ See section 12 (1) (a)

³⁵ Ibid (12) (1) (b)

³⁶ Ibid (12) (1) (c)

³⁷ See generally section 12 (2, 3, and 4)

³⁸ See section 13 (1, 2, 3, 4 and 5)

³⁹ See Sope Williams-Elegbe, ‘The Reform and Regulation of Public Procurement in Nigeria’ note 7, p 349

⁴⁰ This is one of the amendments effected to the Act in 2016 to incorporate consideration of the Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission Act side by side with the Public Procurement Act in procurement of goods, works and services by the federal government and its agencies. The Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission Act primary sets out the requirements for competition and private sector participation in all public procurement as well as requisite approvals for all Public-Private Partnership Contracts. See sections 1-13 of the ICRC Act 2005 for the requirements for competition and private sector participation in public procurement.

⁴¹ Section 60

The Act also applies to all entities outside the description in section 14 (1) (a) so long as those entities “derive at least 35% of the funds appropriated or proposed to be appropriated for any type of procurement described in this Act from the Federation share of the Consolidated Revenue Fund.”⁴²

The Act however is not to “apply to the procurement of special goods, works and services involving national defence or national security unless the President’s express approval has been sought and obtained.”⁴³

It should be noted that exception for the application of the Act to national defence procurement only applies to military hardware or weapons and ammunitions and certainly not to procurement of other goods and services by the defence ministry if they do not fall under the hardware items.⁴⁴

9.0 PRINCIPLES FOR PUBLIC PROCUREMENT

Part IV of the Act deals with the fundamental principles for public procurement. This part has a lone section; section 16 that cover wide range of issues in public procurement.

Except where exemptions are allowed by the Act, all public procurements should be subject to prior thresholds set by the Bureau from time to time pursuant to its powers as contained in section 7 of the Act.⁴⁵ Public procurements should be based on plans that tally with budget and availability of funds appropriated for the procurement and subject to obtaining certificate of no objection from the Bureau.⁴⁶ Public procurements should be based on open competitive bidding,⁴⁷ must be transparent, equitable and ensuring accountability and conformity with the Act.⁴⁸ It should equally be in accordance to procedures and timeline set out by the Act with the aim of achieving value for money and fitness for purpose.⁴⁹

⁴² Section 14 (1) (b)

⁴³ Ibid (2)

⁴⁴ See Sope Williams-Elegbe, ‘The Reform and Regulation of Public Procurement in Nigeria’ note 7, p 347.

⁴⁵ Section 16 (1) (a)

⁴⁶ Ibid (1) (b)

⁴⁷ Ibid (1) (c)

⁴⁸ Ibid (1) (d)

⁴⁹ Ibid (1) (e-g)

The section goes ahead to provide for conditions for the issuance of certificate of no objection by the Bureau, and where no such certificate is issued or the conditions for its issuance are not met, no funds shall be released from the Treasury or Federation Account or any bank account belonging to the procuring entity.⁵⁰ The section further requires all bidders to possess professional, technical, financial ability and legal capacity to enter into a contract and to demonstrate personnel and relevant infrastructure capacity.⁵¹ In addition, bidders should not have any director convicted for any criminal offence relating to fraud or financial impropriety, misrepresentation or falsification of facts in any country.⁵² The procuring entity or the Bureau as the case maybe can require a bidder to provide documentary evidence to prove that the bidder qualifies in accordance with the provisions of the Act.⁵³ The section lists circumstances that their existence in relation to a particular bidder can make the procuring entity or the Bureau to exclude the said bidder from particular procurement proceeding.⁵⁴ Procuring entities are to keep records of procurement proceedings in both files and electronic records within every financial year, and to transmit copies of these records to the Bureau not later than 3 months after the end of the financial year.⁵⁵

In general, this part of the Act can be said to be the heart of the Act as it sets out a number of principles and guidelines on how public procurements are to be conducted. The section covers issues such as the thresholds, procurement plans, definitions and qualifications of bidders, suppliers and service providers as such. It also gives guidelines for issuance of certificate of no objection and the consequences of failure to issue same. It stresses on the importance of open competitive bidding and the conditions for the award of public procurement contract.

9.1 ORGANIZATION OF PROCUREMENTS

Part V of the Act makes series of provisions on how procurements are to be organized by the procuring entities. Section 17 creates approving bodies for the procuring entities; to

⁵⁰ Section 16 (2)

⁵¹ Ibid 16 (6)

⁵² Ibid

⁵³ Ibid

⁵⁴ See section 16 (8) (a-g)

⁵⁵ Ibid (12-13)

which in the case of (i) “a government agency, parastatal, or corporation, a Parastatal Tender Board; and

(ii) a ministry or extra-ministerial entity, the Ministerial Tender Board”.⁵⁶

A procuring entity should have a Procurement Planning Committee⁵⁷ which is to be responsible for planning its procurement by conducting needs assessment and evaluation, identifying goods, works and services it requires by carrying out a market and statistical surveys. The procuring entity should then integrate the identified goods, works and services needed into its yearly budget.⁵⁸ A procuring entity is then expected to advertise and solicit for bids from interested bidders in accordance with the Act. Credible observers representing private sector professional organization, non-governmental organizations working in anti-corruption, transparency and accountability are to be invited by the procuring entity who will observe the procurement process.⁵⁹

A procuring entity will receive bids from interested bidders, evaluate same and make selections in accordance with the Act and Guidelines issued by the Bureau. It should debrief the bid losers if requested, resolve complaints from the bid losers if any, obtain certificate of no objection, execute the contract agreements and announce and publicize the award in the format as stipulated by the Act.⁶⁰ Section 20 rests the overall responsibility of planning, organizing, and evaluation of tenders and execution of procurements on the accounting officer of procuring entity, by ensuring compliance to all the provisions of the Act and the Guidelines as issued by the Bureau.⁶¹

Section 22 established for every procuring entity a tenders board referred to as “the Tenders Board”⁶² to be headed by a chairman of the Tenders Board. It is the responsibility of the Tenders Board to award procurement contracts within the thresholds set by the

⁵⁶ Section 17 (a) (i-ii).

⁵⁷ See section 21 of the Act. The Procurement Planning Committee should consist of the accounting officer of the procuring entity and other members to be drawn from the procurement unit of the procuring entity, the financial unit of the procuring entity, the planning, research and statistics unit of the procuring entity, technical personnel of the procuring entity and legal unit of the procuring entity.

⁵⁸ Section 18

⁵⁹ Section 19

⁶⁰ Ibid

⁶¹ Section 20

⁶² Section 22

Bureau. In cases where a procuring entity sets pre-qualification requirements, the entity shall set out “precise criteria upon which it seeks to give consideration to the applications and in reaching a decision as to which supplier, contractor or service provider qualifies, shall apply only the criteria set out in the prequalification documents and no more”.⁶³ The contractors, suppliers and or consultants that require to be furnished with prequalification documents, the procuring entities shall make sure such documents are made available to those who request for them.⁶⁴ These documents include summary of main terms and conditions required for the contract, the manner and place for the submission of applications to pre-qualify, and any other requirement that may be required by the procuring entity in accordance with the Act.⁶⁵

This part of the Act institutionalizes project procurement planning to ensure that there is proper procurement plan subject to the availability of funds, which must be approved by the Tenders Boards of the procuring entities. The procurements must also be of priority in order to avoid procuring entities embarking on projects that are not of priority to the entity.

10.0 PROCUREMENT METHODS (GOODS AND SERVICES)

The Public Procurement Act adopted the UNCITRAL Model law and the World Bank Procurement Guidelines for the methods and procedures for procurement. Consequently, the Act proposed a number of different procedures that the authorities conducting procurement exercise must adopt.⁶⁶ The processes include open competitive bidding, special and restricted tendering, two-stage tendering, request for quotation and sole source procurement.

10.1 OPEN COMPETITIVE BIDDING

Part V of the Act deals with methods of procurement in goods and services. Section 24 makes it compulsory for every public procurement to be made through open competitive

⁶³ Section 23

⁶⁴ Section 23 (2)

⁶⁵ Section 23 (3)

⁶⁶ See World Bank Guidelines: Procurement of Goods, Works and Non Consulting Services Under IBRD Loans and IDA Credits & Grants By the World Bank Borrowers, 2011, see also UNCITRAL Model Law on Procurement, note 13

bidding,⁶⁷ except otherwise provided by the Act.⁶⁸ Where open competitive bidding is referred to in the Act, it means giving interested bidders equal opportunities to offer goods and works which procurement entity wishes to procure based on defined criteria as set out by the procuring entity.⁶⁹ A winning bid shall be “the lowest evaluated responsive bid⁷⁰ which has been responsive to the bid with regards to work specification and standard”.⁷¹ For the purposes of procurement, invitations to bid may either be by way of National Competitive Bidding⁷² or International Competitive Bidding⁷³ which shall be within the monetary thresholds as set from time to time by the Bureau.⁷⁴ For bids under International Competitive Bidding, they shall be advertised in at least two national newspapers and one internationally recognized publication, official websites of the procuring entities and the website of the Bureau as well as the procurement journal. For bids under the National Competitive Bidding, there is no requirement for publication in internationally recognized publication; however, same must be pasted on the notice boards of procuring entities.⁷⁵ The publication should be made not less than six weeks from the deadline for the submission of bids.⁷⁶

10.2 BID SECURITY

Where the procurement sought to be made exceed the monetary thresholds sets by the Bureau, each of the contractors or suppliers shall give bid security,⁷⁷ an amount not more

⁶⁷ Open competitive bidding is defined by section 60 as “the offer of prices by individuals or firms competing for a contract, privilege or right to supply specified goods, works, construction or services”.

⁶⁸ Section 24 (1)

⁶⁹ Sub section (2)

⁷⁰ This is defined in section 60 as “the lowest price bid amongst the bids that meet all the technical requirements and standards as contained in the tender document.”

⁷¹ Sub section (3)

⁷² National Competitive Bidding is defined by section 60 as “the solicitation of bids from domestic contractors and suppliers registered or incorporated to carry on business under the Nigerian Law”.

⁷³ International Competitive Bidding on the other hand is defined as “the solicitation of bids from both domestic and foreign contractors and suppliers”. Section 60.

⁷⁴ Section 25 (1)

⁷⁵ Section 25 (2) (i and ii)

⁷⁶ Ibid

⁷⁷ Bid security is defined by section 60 to mean “a form of security assuring the bidder shall not withdraw a bid within the period specified for acceptance and shall execute a written contract within the time specified in the bid”.

than 2% of the bid price by way of bank guarantee to be issued by a reputable bank in the country.⁷⁸

Bids are to be submitted in writing and signed by officials authorized to bind the bidders to a contract and to be put in a sealed envelope.⁷⁹ All bids are to be made in English and shall be deposited in a temper-proof bid-box at the bidding entities, and a receipt shall be issued by a bidding entity containing date and time the bid was deposited.⁸⁰ Bids submitted after the deadline shall not be opened and shall be returned to the bidders, and no communication shall take place between the contractors who submitted bids with a procuring entity other than as provided by the Act.⁸¹

A procuring entity can reject a bid or cancel entirely the procurement proceedings in the public interest without incurring any liability to the bidders who submitted bids or whose bids were rejected as the case maybe.⁸²

10.3 OPENING OF BIDS

Section 30 of the Act provides for the process of opening of bids submitted by the bidders. The bids opening shall be attended by the bidders or their representatives and any interested member of the public.

The attendees present during the opening of the bids shall be permitted to examine the bids to ensure that the envelopes have not been tempered with before the opening. The names and addresses of all bidders with the total amount of each bid shall be called to the hearing of all present, and this shall be recorded by the Secretary of the Tenders Board or his delegate in the minutes of the bid opening.⁸³

Bids are to be examined first and foremost to ensure that they have met all the requirements of the procurement as stipulated in the bidding documents.⁸⁴ Clarifications where necessary for bids submitted may be sought from bidders in order to assist in evaluation and comparisons of bids. However, no clarifications can be sought in respect of

⁷⁸ Section 26 (1)

⁷⁹ Section 27 (1)

⁸⁰ Sub section (2, 3 and 4)

⁸¹ Sub section (5 and 6)

⁸² Section 28

⁸³ See section 30 (a-d)

⁸⁴ Section 31 (1)

changes in prices, changes in substance in a bid, changes to make unresponsive bid responsive.⁸⁵ Purely arithmetical errors can be corrected and notice be giving to the supplier or contractor who submitted the bid.⁸⁶

Major deviations in a bid shall result in rejection of such bid whereas for minor deviations, clarifications may be sought from the supplier or contractor submitting the said bid.⁸⁷

Major deviations which attract rejection include: unacceptable sub-contracting, unacceptable time schedule where time is of essence, unacceptable price adjustment, the fact that a bidder is not qualified or is ineligible, the fact that a bidder is uninvited, any bid received after the date and time for submission stipulated in the procurement documents.⁸⁸ Where bids are rejected for major deviations, a letter shall be written to the bidders stating the reasons for rejection and no permission is to be made to amend or correct the deviations that led to the rejection.⁸⁹

Minor deviations that do not attract rejection of a bid include: difference in standard, alternative designs, omission in minor items, arithmetical errors. These also include different methods of construction, completion period where time is not of essence, payment terms, and any condition that is of little significance on the bid.⁹⁰ Where minor deviations are discovered a written clarification may be offered by the contractors or suppliers.⁹¹ Suppliers, who do not accept correction of a minor deviation, shall have their bids rejected and notified in writing promptly.⁹²

10.4 SELECTION OF BIDS

Bids are to be evaluated and compared using methods already specified in the solicitations documents in order to determine and select the lowest evaluated responsive bid from the rest of the bids that responded to the solicitation.⁹³ The lowest evaluated responsive bid

⁸⁵ Sub section (2 and 3) (a, b, c and d)

⁸⁶ Sub section (4 and 5)

⁸⁷ Sub section 6

⁸⁸ Sub section (7) (a, b, c and d)

⁸⁹ Sub section (8)

⁹⁰ Sub section (10) (a-p)

⁹¹ Sub section (11)

⁹² Sub section (12)

⁹³ Section 32 (1 and 2)

shall be declared the successful bid from the bidders responsive to the solicitation.⁹⁴ However, notwithstanding the provision of subsection 1, the procuring entity can select as successful bid a bid that is not the lowest responsive evaluated bid provided they can show good grounds derived from the provisions of the Act.⁹⁵

Margin of preferences⁹⁶ shall be given to domestic bidders as against the foreign bidders in the evaluation of tenders, where the procuring entity has allowed such preferences, the solicitation documents shall clearly indicate such preferences given to domestic bidders.⁹⁷

Margin of preferences can only be given under international competitive bidding.⁹⁸

A contractor or supplier whose bid emerged successful and awarded the contract can apply for a mobilization fee of not more than 30% maybe paid to him in accordance with the Act.⁹⁹

Procurement entities shall keep records of comprehensive procurement proceedings and shall make same available on request to suppliers, contractors, consultants who participated in the bidding process in question. Same records shall equally be made available to the Bureau for inspection or to investigators appointed by the Bureau or Auditor-General upon request.¹⁰⁰

11.0 SPECIAL AND RESTRICTED METHODS OF PROCUREMENT

The Act under part VII, covering sections 39 to 43, makes provisions for special methods of procurement. In this part, the Act provides different modes which can be adopted for procurement by procuring entities.

11.1 TWO STAGE TENDERING

Section 39 provides for two-stage tendering¹⁰¹ to be used in a number of circumstances as provided by the Act.¹⁰² For instance;

⁹⁴ Section 33 (1)

⁹⁵ Sub section (3)

⁹⁶ Margin of preference means the extra mark up on price allowed any domestic contractor or supplier bidding under international competitive bidding without otherwise disadvantageous to the bid in terms of price". Section 60

⁹⁷ Section 34 (1 and 2)

⁹⁸ Sub section (3)

⁹⁹ See section 35 (1 and 2)

¹⁰⁰ See generally section 38 (1-5)

¹⁰¹ The Act did not define two-stage tendering, but the following subsections of section 39 described what two-stage tendering is about and how it is done.

¹⁰² Section 39 (2)

- (a) where it is not feasible for a procuring entity to formulate detailed specifications for what it wants to procure, it can seek proposals on various ways of meeting its needs to be submitted by contractors and suppliers,
- (b) Where the nature of the goods or services it requires is such that it changes rapidly as a result of changes in technology;
- (c) where the procuring entity intends to enter into a research, study, experiments, or development;
- (d) where there is consideration for national security thereby making two-stage procurement the most appropriate method to be adopted; or
- (e) Where open competitive procurement methods have been used but not successful.¹⁰³

The procedure in two-stage tendering is the same as in open competitive bidding with the only difference being that in two-stage tendering the bidders will not include prices in their first proposals. The proposals will only contain information relating to technical aspect of the project and some contractual terms and conditions.¹⁰⁴ Only those suppliers and or contractors whose tenders conformed substantially to what the procuring entity desires will be invited to submit final tenders for the second stage of the process. Prices are included in the final tenders to be submitted by the contractors which are then compared to select the successful one.¹⁰⁵ The rest of the process in terms of rejection and reasons leading to rejection and communication of rejection is all the same as in the case of open competitive bidding.¹⁰⁶

11.2 RESTRICTED TENDERING

Restricted tendering may be adopted by procuring entities under certain circumstances and subject to the approval of the Bureau.¹⁰⁷ Restricted tendering may be adopted where for some reasons the goods, works, and services are only available or offered by a limited number of contractors or suppliers,¹⁰⁸ or where the time and cost of examining tenders from large number of contractors and suppliers is disproportionate to the value of the

¹⁰³ Ibid

¹⁰⁴ Sub section 4 (a-b); see also Sope Williams-Elegbe, 'The Reform and Regulation of Public Procurement in Nigeria' note 6, p 350.

¹⁰⁵ Sub section (5, 6 and 7)

¹⁰⁶ Ibid

¹⁰⁷ Section 40

¹⁰⁸ Sub section (1) (a)

goods, works or services required.¹⁰⁹ Where this is the case, a procuring entity can adopt restricted tendering to seek for tenders from suppliers and contractors who can offer such goods, works or services. The selection for the award of the contract amongst the selected contractors and suppliers must however be in the most transparent and non-discriminatory manner.¹¹⁰

11.3 REQUEST FOR QUOTATIONS

Procuring entity may also resort to requesting for quotations to be submitted by contractors and suppliers for goods, works and services that their value does not exceed a sum set out in the procurement regulations.¹¹¹ Where request for quotations is adopted by procuring entity, quotations should be requested from at least three unrelated contractors or suppliers who shall give only one quotation each and shall not be allowed to change or vary their quotations.¹¹² No negotiations should take place between procuring entities and contractors and suppliers who submit their quotations. Contracts should be awarded to the most qualified quotation submitted to the procuring entities.¹¹³

11.4 DIRECT PROCUREMENT (EMERGENCY PROCUREMENT)

The Act in sections 42 and 43 provide for both direct and emergency modes of procurement by the procuring entities. Section 42 provides situations where goods and or services are to be procured for emergency purposes where those goods and services can only be supplied by few contractors or suppliers.¹¹⁴ Or where there is an urgent need for such goods, works or services that conducting the normal process of procurement will waste time or is even impracticable.¹¹⁵ Procuring entity adopting direct method of procurement can invite proposals or price quotations from single contractor or supplier, reasons for adoption of this method must however be captured in the records of the procurement exercise.¹¹⁶

¹⁰⁹ Sub section (2) (b)

¹¹⁰ Ibid

¹¹¹ Section 41

¹¹² Subsection (2) and (3 b)

¹¹³ Subsection (4 and 5)

¹¹⁴ Section 42 (1) (a)

¹¹⁵ Sub section (1) (b); paragraphs (c, d, e and f) give additional situations that may necessitate procuring entity adopting direct method of procurement.

¹¹⁶ Subsection 2 (a and b)

For emergency method for procurement, this is allowed in situations where the country is threatened by or confronted with a disaster, catastrophe, war or insurrection or act of God.¹¹⁷ Or where goods, equipment, building or capital good need urgent maintenance for which its condition may deteriorate if such maintenance is not procured.¹¹⁸ Procurement can be done direct in any of the situations mentioned in this section as long as the situations warranting same persist.

11.5 PROCUREMENT OF CONSULTANTS (SERVICES)

Part VIII of the Act, covering sections 44-52, makes provisions for the procurement of services from consultants. Section 45 requires procuring entities wishing to procure unascertained services from consultants such as “research, experiment, study or development”¹¹⁹ to follow the laid down processes by publishing notice of expression of interest in at least two national newspapers and the procurement journal.¹²⁰ The procuring entities can equally approach directly the consultants to request for proposals in respect of the services required.¹²¹

The rest of the processes of selection and award of the contract for the services of consultants is the same with what is provided in part V of the Act for general procurement of goods and services. These are in respect of the contents of the proposals,¹²² clarification and modification of request for proposals,¹²³ criteria for evaluation of proposals¹²⁴ selection and award of contract.¹²⁵

12.0 PROCUREMENT SURVEILLANCE AND REVIEW

Section 53 of the Act empowers the Bureau to review and recommend for investigation by a relevant authority on a suspicion of foul play in the conduct of procurement proceedings by any procuring entity where it is considered criminal investigation is required in that

¹¹⁷ See section 43 (1) (a)

¹¹⁸ Ibid paragraph (b)

¹¹⁹ Section 45 (1)

¹²⁰ Subsection (2)

¹²¹ Subsection (3)

¹²² Section 46

¹²³ Section 47

¹²⁴ Section 49

¹²⁵ Section 50 and 51

regard.¹²⁶ A bidder can equally seek administrative review of the procurement process for any perceived breach or omission from procuring entities.¹²⁷

13.0 DISPOSAL OF PUBLIC PROPERTY

Most part of the Act deals with procurement of goods and services by the government's agencies and parastatals, part X of the Act however, deals with disposal of public property by procuring entities. Section 55 of the Act states that part X of the Act shall apply subject to the Public Enterprises (Commercialization and Commercialization) Act of 1990. Subsection 2 of the Act empowers procuring entities to dispose-off public property. Subsection 5 defines what public property subject to disposal is. This comprises of both tangible and non-tangible assets created or acquired through public expenditure, gift, intellectual rights, financial instruments, or through goodwill and or gift of the Federal Government.¹²⁸

14.0 CODE OF CONDUCT

Part XI of the Act mandates the Bureau to develop a code of conduct governing procurement activities by the procuring entities.¹²⁹ The Act requires the conducts of all persons involved in public procurement to be based on the "principles of honesty, accountability, transparency, fairness and equity."¹³⁰ Accordingly, the Bureau in accordance with the provision of section 57 issued a Bureau of Public Procurement Code of Conduct for Public Officers Involved with Procurement.¹³¹ The Code seeks to guide the conduct of public officers in public procurement by prohibiting any activity that may lead to perception of unfairness against any bidder or service provider, prohibiting receiving bribes from bidders and also prohibiting manifestation of any conflict of interests in the procurement process.¹³² The idea is to make all public officers involved in procurement process responsible and liable in cases of infractions.

¹²⁶ See section 53 of the Act.

¹²⁷ Section 54 of the Act.

¹²⁸ See subsection 5

¹²⁹ Section 57

¹³⁰ See section 57 (2); see also supra note 6, Sope Williams-Elegbe, 'The Reform and Regulation of Public Procurement in Nigeria' p 355.

¹³¹ Code of Conduct for Public Officers under the Public Procurement Act, 2007 (as amended).

¹³² Supra note 6, Sope Williams-Elegbe, 'The Reform and Regulation of Public Procurement in Nigeria'.

15.0 OFFENCES

The Act under part XII identified some offences relating to public procurement and spelt out punishments for such offences. Section 58 (1) prescribes not less than 5 calendar years but not exceeding 10 calendar years imprisonment without option of a fine as punishment for any person who contravenes the provisions of the Act.¹³³ The Federal High Court has the exclusive jurisdiction to try offences under the Act.¹³⁴

Offences that attract punishment include procurement collusion, or “attempting to enter into collusive agreement between suppliers.”¹³⁵ It is also a punishable offence under the Act to commit or attempt to commit any procurement fraud through corrupt acts, undue interest, bribery, favor, or unlawful influence.¹³⁶ Any attempt to give or receive bribery directly or indirectly in order to gain unfair advantage in the award of a contract is a criminal offence punishable by the Act.¹³⁷ Tender splitting to evade monetary threshold, bid-rigging,¹³⁸ fraudulent misrepresentation by altering procurement documents or using fake documents in order to influence the result of tender proceedings, are all criminal offences punishable under the Act.¹³⁹

16.0 CHALLENGES

The Public Procurement Act is a milestone Nigeria has taken in term of promoting accountability, integrity, transparency and good governance in the procurement process. This can be seen in the provision of the Act which encourages open competition,¹⁴⁰ publicity of contract opportunities, criminalizing certain procurement offences, provides avenues for administrative review, establishment of institutions which overlooks implementation of the Act. This is a laudable milestone. However, implementation remains a bottleneck as it is bedeviled with irregularities, corruption and unethical practices.

¹³³ Section 58(1)

¹³⁴ See section 58 (2)

¹³⁵ Subsection (4)

¹³⁶ Subsection (4) (b)

¹³⁷ Ibid (4) (c)

¹³⁸ This is defined by subsection (10) as a situation where bids are prearranged or otherwise engaging in acts that have the effect of restricting directly or indirectly free and open competition.

¹³⁹ See generally section 58 (4) (a-h) of the Act

¹⁴⁰ Section 1(c)

The most prominent of the challenges in public procurement in Nigeria is the issue of corruption in the form of bribery to secure contract, meddling by high ranking politicians who put pressure and manipulate the whole process for their own interest thereby defeating the principles of accountability and transparency in the procurement process.¹⁴¹ Procurement contracts are awarded to companies belonging to highly placed politicians who manipulate the process.¹⁴² “Thus, corruption in the public sector is hugely dependent on the manipulation of the procurement framework and public financial management more generally.¹⁴³ Political interference could take so many forms as exemplified in a report by public and Private Development Center (PPDC) as follows:

- i. Failure to inaugurate the National Council of Public Procurement;
- ii. Approval of contracts by the Federal Executive Council (FEC);
- iii. Approval of the condition of service at the BPP;
- iv. Approval of policies and guidelines issued by the BPP;
- v. Official communication between the Ministers and the BPP on procurement matters;
- vi. Influencing contract award through subtle and non-subtle means.¹⁴⁴

Research has shown that there is poor knowledge of the procurement Act and procedures by the procuring entities and lack of expertise of the procuring personnel.¹⁴⁵ Though the BPP is charged with the responsibility of organizing training and Programmes for procurement professional, research indicates that training and researches are conducted

¹⁴¹ See Sope Williams-Elegbe, ‘Systematic Corruption and Public Procurement in Developing Countries: Are there any Solutions?’ [2018] *Journal of Public Procurement* (18(2) P 131-147

¹⁴² Ngozi Nwagwugwu, Adetunji Olumuyiwa Adebayo, ‘Appraisal of Integrity in Public Procurement Process in Nigeria’ [July 2015] (Vol. 17, Issue 7) *IOSR Journal of Business and Management* (IOSR-JBM) Ver.1. See also F. Oyebamiji Florence, ‘Implementation of Public Procurement Act, 2007: Evidence from Nigeria’ (1(4): 1-9) *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, Article No. SAJSSE42866

¹⁴³ See Sope Williams-Elegbe, ‘Systematic Corruption and Public Procurement in Developing Countries: Are there any Solutions?’ note 141, p.140

¹⁴⁴ Walking the Path of Procurement Reforms in Nigeria: Compliance with Public Procurement Act, 2007 (2012) An Initiative of the Public and Private Development Center (PPDC)

¹⁴⁵ *Ibid*

at a slow pace and perhaps to small units and as such the impact may not likely be visible and felt. Also the quality and standard may not be adequate enough to show much impact.¹⁴⁶ The complexity of the Act makes it a challenge to the successful implementation of the Act. This can be seen from researches that reveal the legal complexities the contracting organizations are required to satisfy before they are considered for public procurement process.¹⁴⁷

The Procurement Act has provided for procurement offences and has provided for punishment for breach of the provisions of the Act. However, the anti-corruption agencies hardly prosecute procurement offences. This has become a bottleneck as offenders go with impunity. Prosecuting offenders would serve as deterrence to others as aptly put that: When sections are implemented through imprisonment, or in accordance with other legal prescription, it would serve as deterrence to others. Besides, the Act cannot be said to be working when breaches are not sanctioned. The law has to be implemented to the latter.¹⁴⁸

17.0 RECOMMENDATION

The paper recommends the followings:

1. Government should do more in the fight against corruption in the public procurement process. This becomes necessary as the Act itself was enacted to cure corruption, irregularities and unethical practices that marred procurement process before the enactment of the Act.
2. As a rider to the above recommendation, politicians have no place in the procurement process which is purely a technical and administrative process not politicking, hence, government should limit political interference in the procurement process.
3. Political interference would be greatly reduced if the government will inaugurate the National Council of Public Procurement (NCP) and allow it to perform its

¹⁴⁶ Deji Rufus Ogunsemi and Oluwaseji Alabi Awodele, 'Assessment of the Challenges Facing the Effective Operation of the Nigerian Public Procurement Act, 2007'[November 2015] (Vol. III, Issue II), *International Journal of Economic, Commerce and Management*

¹⁴⁷ Ibid

¹⁴⁸ Keynote Address Delivered by Chief Olusegun Obasanjo GCFR former president of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, to mark the 10th Anniversary of the Public Procurement Reforms in Nigeria, [July-September 2011] *the Public Procurement Journal*, 11th Edition, Bureau Public Procurement , Abuja

function as stipulated under the Act.¹⁴⁹ As it is now, the Federal Executive Council (FEC) which is purely political set up, has hijacked the functions of the NCPP compromising the core principles of procurement process.

4. The anti-corruption agencies should live up to their expectation by proper investigation and prosecution of breaches of the procurement Act. The provisions should be implemented to the latter if the process is to be seen as transparent and accountable.
5. Improving the quality and standard of training of procurement entities and professionals will go a long way in equipping them with the required knowledge necessary in performing their functions as required by the Act.

18.0 CONCLUSION

The Bureau for Public Procurement Act was promulgated based on the recommendations of the World Bank following the publication of its country assessment report on public procurement in 2007 which exposed the irregularities, inconsistencies and high level of corruption going on in the public procurement process in Nigeria. The Act therefore seeks to entrench the international best practices regarding public procurement process. There is no doubt that the Act is a major milestone in the development of standards in the public procurement process in Nigeria.

¹⁴⁹ Sections 1-2 Public Procurement Act, 2007